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Weed–Competitive Rice Cultivars under Natural Weed Pressure in Malinyi District, Morogoro, Tanzania

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Abstract

Weed-competitive rice cultivars and weeding interval are viable tools for integrated weed management in rice field among other control methods which may reduce effect of weeds. Based on these ideas, a field trial was piloted in 2021 in the rainy season at Kiswago Village (located at 8° 54' 0" south, 36° 17' 0" east) to determine the weed competitiveness of rice cultivars and appropriate weeding regime. Four cultivars were evaluated under natural weed pressure conditions. The trial was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design in split plot arrangement with three replications. Sowing space was 25 by 20 cm for interrow and intrarow respectively. Data collected for crop were; Plant height, number of tillers and leaves, duration to 90% grain maturity, panicle weight, grain filling, weight of 1000 seeds, grain yield, relative and straw biomass, for weeds were; weed count and biomass. Significant differences among means were separated by Tukey honest and least significance difference test (LSD) at $p \leq 0.05$. Out of six weed species observed, *Paspalum scrobiculatum* with greater Summed dominance ration (39.60), indicated that had greater contribution in competition. The results revealed significant differences ($p < .001$) in relative yield loss ranging from 39.54% to 63.84%. Karimata with lowest value demonstrated high tolerance to weeds while SARO 5 with high value had less tolerance. Twice and more weeding had positive effect ($p < .001$) on grain yield in all cultivar tested. Weed drymatter and grain yield had significant negative relationship ($R^2 = 0.2691$). Karimata contained high weed competitive ability than others three cultivars tested. Farmers are recommended to use twice weeding (at 15 and 45 DAE) to reduce cost, save time and increase productivity, more research is requested to evaluate karimata weed competitive potentials and control methods of *Paspalum scrobiculatum* and *Ischaemum rugosum* weed species.

Key words: Rice cultivar; weed pressure; yield; relative yield loss; summed dominance ratio

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Based on water availability and topography, rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is grown in four ecosystems: (i) rain fed upland rice on the plateau and hydroponic slopes (39%), (ii) rain fed lowland rice in the valley bottoms and flood plains (33%), (iii) irrigated rice delta flood plains and highlands (19%) and (iv) deep-water floating rice along the river and mangrove-swamp rice in lagoon (Mkanthama *et al.*, 2018; Rugumamu, 2014; Rao *et al.*, 2017). From the genus *Oryza*, rice is an annual grass. There are 23 recognized species of rice, of which two have a high commercial value and are widely grown (Teeken *et al.*, 2012). There are two types of rice: *Oryza sativa* (Asian rice), which is grown all over the world, and *Oryza glaberrima* (African rice), which is farmed in South Africa (Teeken *et al.*, 2012). The indica species from tropical Asia is frequently identified by its long, wide to narrow, light green leaves, abundant tillering, long and thin grains, and numerous

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secondary ramifications. *Oryza glaberrima* comes from the Niger River's interior delta and is distinguished by a lot of vegetative growth, short, rounded ligules, no or few secondary ramifications, crimson caryopsis, and a protracted dormancy (Coudert *et al.*, 2010). Rice cultivars differ greatly in the overall productivity (Dimaano *et al.*, 2017). Kitilu *et al.* (2019) presented that grain yield of different cultivars such as SARO 5 yielded 7 – 8.5 t/ha and NERICA1, 3 – 4.5t/ha.

Rice is grown under varying conditions of altitude, from sea level to 3000 meters high. It requires hot and humid climate, with prolonged sunshine and reliable water supply and temperature range of 21 to 37° C. Clay soils are most suited for rice growth due to capability of holding water for long and sustain crop (Fageria, 2013).

Planting weed-contaminated crop seeds affect weed competitiveness of rice cultivar because act as source and early infestation of clean fields with weeds. Weeds such as *Ishaemum rogosum* (Saramolla grass), *Paspalum scroculatum* (kodo millet), *Echinochloa colona* (Jungle rice), red rice and *Ageratum conyzoides* (Goat weed), are distributed when planting rice seeds (Martin *et al.*, 2017; Gervilla *et al.*, 2019). Moisture regimes of the soil affects growth of weeds and their competition referring to submerged, water-saturated, and usual dry land conditions. The biomass of weeds per unit area is higher in water-saturated and dry land fields, but lower in submerged fields (Samoy-Pascual *et al.*, 2020). Degree of weed pressure in rice fields affect competitive ability of rice cultivars. The best weed control knowledge, however, will not prevent yield losses due to weeds when rice is grown continually on the same land (Upasani *et al.*, 2014; Andres *et al.*, 2021). Crop rotations alone are incomplete in preventing weeds from causing yield losses in rice (Pardo *et al.*, 2021). Integrated system of weed control is required to prevent weeds from increasing to economic threshold levels (Jiya *et al.*, 2019).

Crop competitiveness is made up of two components: weed suppressive ability, or the crop's capacity to limit weed growth in terms of dry matter accumulation, and tolerance to weed infestation, or the capacity to maintain high yields under weedy conditions (Andrew *et al.*, 2015; Rasmussen *et al.*, 2021). However, there aren't many rice genotypes known to have greater weed competitiveness (Dimaano *et al.*, 2017; Fahad *et al.*, 2019). The growth and competitiveness of plants are influenced by the availability of nutrients, water, and light. The amount of these resources in a rice environment is theoretically set; what one plant species uses cannot be used by another. In general, there is a negative relationship between rice yield and weed biomass, meaning that more weed biomass results in lower rice output (Nazir *et al.*, 2022; Thi *et al.*, 2020). The ability of different weed species to compete with rice varies (Gharde *et al.*, 2018).

The main factors influencing the relative competitiveness of annual and perennial weeds are their species and the environmental factors in which they are flourishing (Teka, 2014). Crop height appeared to have the greatest impact on competitive ability, with the shortest cultivars experiencing the largest yield reductions and allowing the greatest weed growth (Sunyob *et al.*, 2015). According to Andrew *et al.* (2015), yield gains of 7– 9% have been identified in “competitive” aerobic cultivars when compared with “noncompetitive” cultivars. Also critical period of weed control is one of the important tools in integrated weed management (Kifelew *et al.*, 2015). It is an intermission in the life cycle of a crop which must be kept without weed, is not necessarily the time of extreme interference, but is the number of weeks after crop emergence during which a crop must be free of weeds in order to prevent yield losses (Ismaila *et al.*, 2013; Kifelew *et al.*, 2015). In rice, this is before it has formed a congested canopy and when the crop is tillering (Sebastain *et al.*, 2013). Weed management during the early growth stages of rice is essential to reduce the competition (Saito *et al.*, 2018). Critical period of weed control is one of the important tools in integrated weed management (Kifelew *et al.*, 2015).

Weeds cause 15 to 20% of rice production loss, but under extreme circumstances, the yield loss might reach 50% or even 100% (Sureshkumar *et al.*, 2016). According to research by Rodenburg *et al.* (2015) and Gharde *et al.* (2018), weeds can reduce rice yields by 12 to 98%, depending on the method used to establish the crop. Yield losses are greater in rice systems that use direct seed sowing than in transplanted rice. Yield

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losses due to uncontrolled weed growth and weed competition were least in transplanted rice, and the highest in rainfed direct sowing rice without proper land preparation (Bajwa *et al.*, 2017; Ghosh *et al.*, 2017; Ismaila *et al.*, 2013). The amount of yield loss also depends on the weed density (high density may cause high competition which lead to greater yield loss), type of weeds (more competitive weeds cause greater yield loss, example; wild rice) and the competition duration (longer period of competition cause greater yield loss than shorter period of competition) (Touré *et al.*, 2011; Gharde *et al.*, 2018).

In addition to drastically lowering rice yields, weeds raise cultivation costs and decrease input efficiency. In addition, it serves as a substitute host for a number of illnesses and insect pests alters the ecosystem's aesthetics and natural biodiversity, has an impact on cattle and human health, and lowers grain quality (Teka, 2014; Swanton *et al.*, 2015; Jha *et al.*, 2017). A successful weed management program needs to take into account a number of variables that vary from crop to crop and from season to season, such as planting date and climate (Danimaigoro *et al.*, 2019). In between the life cycle and prior to seeding, weed management can start. Since there is no one solution that works for all weeds, an integrated weed management system should be taken into consideration (Alagbo *et al.*, 2022). Kone *et al.* (2014) claimed that using cultivars that are competitive with weeds may help control weeds effectively and raise rice yield. Finding the competitive rice cultivars under natural weed pressure and figuring out the ideal number of weedings to achieve maximum yield were the goals of this study.

1.2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.2.1 Site description

Field study was conducted to determine the effect of weed competition on the performance of rice cultivars in direct-sowing conditions in the rainy seasons from January to July, 2021. The experiment was laid out at Kiswago village, Malinyi District (located at 8° 54' 0" south, 36° 17' 0" east, elevation of 275 metre above sea level with an average rainfall of 800 to 1600 mm per year) in Morogoro region (Fig.3.1). In 2021, the monthly mean rain fall was 241.7, 156.1, 230.6, 319.7, 61.4 and 8.6 mm for January to June, respectively (TMA, 2021). The soil type at the experimental site was sandy clay loam with 1.25% organic matter and a pH of 5.92. The total N content in the soil was 0.14%.The available P (0.1mg/kg) and K contents (0.90Cmol+/kg) in soil. Field had the history of rice production for more than 5 years. Soil was analyzed at SUA Soil Science Laboratory.

Figure 1.1: Map showing Experimental site

1.2.2 Experimental Material

Three local rice cultivars; Karimata, Kisegesi and Mbawambili (Hubert *et al.*, 2016; Nkuba *et al.*, 2016) were bought from farmers and one improved variety SARO 5 (TXD 306) from TARI Ifakara. Local

cultivar characterized by tall stature, moderately short duration to maturity (100 – 110 days), grows well under stagnant water. They are aromatic cultivars with moderate yielding of 1.5 – 4 t ha⁻¹ (Kitilu *et al.*, 2019). TXD 306 (SARO 5), an improved rice variety registered in Tanzania, was developed and released by TARI Dakawa in 2002. It is a high yielding semi aromatic (7.0 – 8.5 t ha⁻¹), with moderate duration (120 - 125 days) and is a photosensitive variety. It can tolerate water logging (Kitilu *et al.*, 2019; Kangile *et al.*, 2018).

1.2.3 Experimental design and treatments

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design in split plot arrangement with three replications (Sunyob *et al.*, 2015). The net size of each main plot was 15 meters and sub plot was 9 m² (3.0 m × 3.0 m). The space between replications was 1 meter. An alley of 0.5 m separated subplots and 1m separated main plots, while border space was 1.5 m and total area was 74 m by 14 m.

Spacing used was 25 cm by 20 cm for inter and intra row, respectively. Four rice cultivars in Main plots had five subplots (weeding regimes). Weeding regimes were no weeding all season, one weeding at 15 days after emergence (DAE), two weedings at 15 and 45 DAE, three weedings at 15, 30 and 45 DAE and as weed free, weeding at 15, 30, 45 and 60 DAE.

1.2.4 Crop management

Fields were prepared by cultivating twice using a mold board plow, followed by harrowing and leveling with hand hoe (Ismaila *et al.*, 2013). Seeds were sown by a single-row dibbling at a seeding rate of 30 kg ha⁻¹. Weeding was done as explained in section 3.2.3 above and source of water was rainfall. The Nitrogen (N) fertilizer at the rate of 50 kg N ha⁻¹ was top dressed once at 45 DAS (Sunyob *et al.*, 2015).

1.2.5 Methods

1.2.5.1 Crop data

During data collection, fifteen (15) rice plants were chosen at random from 4m² center of each plot then tagged and used to record Plant height, number of tillers and leaves. Rice plant height in centimeter was measured by using tape measure from the ground level to the tip of flag leaf. Data taking repeated in two weeks interval. Fifty four (54) rice plant sample in 4m² centre of each plot used to determine number of days that 90% of panicles were at maturity stage. At maturity stage, after harvesting, rice panicles from 10 rice plants chosen at randomly from 4m² centre of each plot were counted and weighed. The average panicle weight was recorded. Rice panicles harvested from the 4m² centre of each plot, threshed, dried until constant (at moisture content range of 10 – 14% (Mbie, 2017)) weight and then weighed to determine grain yield in t/ha. From grain one thousand seeds from each plot were weighed to determine weight. Rice straws at maturity stage (after removing panicles) were cut at ground level from 1m² center of each plot and then weighed for fresh weight. The biomass were sun-dried followed by oven-dried at 70 °C for 72 hours until constant weight. Weight stated in t/ha.

1.2.5.2 Weed data

All weeds in 1 by 1 meter centre of each plot were identified and counted by species in 15 days interval and recorded. All weeds from 1 m² center of each plot were clipped to ground level, separated by species, weighed for fresh biomass, and then followed by sun drying. After oven dried for 72 hours at 70 °C, were weighed to get dry biomass in t/ha.

1.2.6 Statistical analyses

In assessing the variability of measured variables (in rice or weeds), a split – plot design of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed following rice cultivars (Mbawambili, Karimata, Kisegesi and SARO 5 – TXD 306) and weeding regimes (not weeded – control, weeded once, weeded twice, weeded thrice, weeded four times). The fixed main effects in the design were the rice cultivars considered as the main plot and weeding regimes as the sub-plot whereas replicates were treated as random effect. The significant treatment means with respect to the sole effect of rice cultivars or weeding regimes were compared using the least significance difference (LSD) while significant means

resulting from interactions between rice cultivars and weeding regimes were compared using the standard error of differences of means (SED) at 5% threshold by Tukey’s post hoc multiple comparisons (Baker *et al.*, 2021). Computer package GENSTAT software version 16 was used. The factors effect model as shown in equation 1

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + (\alpha\beta)_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where

Y_{ij} is observed measured variable in the ij th factors; μ is the overall (grand) mean of the measured variable; α_i and β_j are the main effects of the factors rice cultivars and weeding regimes respectively; $(\alpha\beta)_{ij}$ is the two – way (first order) interactions between the factors rice cultivars and weeding regimes; ε_{ij} is the random error associated with the observation of the measured variables in the ij th factors.

The relative yield loss (YL) of the crop faced by weed competition under field conditions was estimated using the following equation (Ahmed *et al.*, 2020).

$$RYL\% = \left[1 - \frac{YCW}{YCM}\right] \times 100, \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

YCW and YCM= crop yields in competition with weeds and in weed-free conditions, respectively. Total weed density and total weed dry weight were recorded and expressed as weed count/ m² and t/ha, respectively. Degree of infestation (relative density) of individual weed species {Density of a given weed species/ Total weed density} × 100} was also calculated (Rahman *et al.*, 2017; Travlos *et al.*, 2018; Varsha *et al.*, 2019). Weed dry biomass data collected was correlated to rice grain yield in order to determine their relationship (Rahman *et al.*, 2017; Dimaano *et al.*, 2017).

The summed dominance ratio (SDR) was calculated to identify the dominant weed species using the following equations (Islam *et al.*, 2021):

$$SDR \text{ of a weed species} = \frac{\text{Relative density} + \text{Relative weed biomass}}{2} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where

$$\text{Relative density (\%)} = \frac{\text{Density of a given weed species}}{\text{Total weed density}} * 100 \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$\text{Relative weed biomass (\%)} = \frac{\text{Biomass of a given weed species}}{\text{Total weed biomass}} * 100 \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

1.3 RESULTS

In this study the interactions of factors (weeding regimes and rice cultivars) for all variables had no statistical significant difference with p values ranging from 0.058 to 0.944 which are greater than 0.05 significance level. Therefore factor based (main effects) results are presented.

1.3.1 Weed species composition

Six weed species belonging to three different families were identified, among them two were grasses, two were broadleaves, and two were sedge. The most dominant weed species encountered was *Paspalum scrobiculatum* with greater summed dominance ratio and the least dominant one was *Cyperus rotundus* with smaller summed dominance ratio (Table 1.1).

Table1.1: Weed species and their summed dominance ratio

SN	Weed species	Type	Family	Lifecycle	Relative Density	Relative biomass	Summed dominance ratio
1	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Grass	Poaceae	Perennial	37.40	49.79	43.60
2	<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	Grass	poaceae	Perennial	19.40	27.78	23.59

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Salsb.							
3	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i> Cav.	Broadleaf	Asteraceae	Annual	18.20	18.57	18.39
4	<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> L.	Sedge	Cyperaceae	Perennial	14.00	7.26	10.63
5	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Broadleaf	Asteraceae	Annual	10.00	3.44	6.72
6	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Sedge	Cyperaceae	Perennial	1.00	1.15	1.08

1.3.2 Plant heights (Cm)

Weeding regimes were assessed for their effect on rice plant heights. Table 1.2 illustrates the average plant heights of rice plants at 40, 54, 68 and 82 days after sowing under five weeding regimes. There was no statistical significant influence of weeding regime on rice plant heights 40 days after sowing (p-value = 0.172) at a 5% significance level. None of the weeded plots had plants that were taller than the non-weeded plots (controls). At 54 DAS, weeding regimes had significant impact on average rice plant heights (p-value 0.003) (Tble 1.2). Plant heights averaged 49.81 cm in plots where weeds were controlled twice (at 15 and 45 DAE), while plant heights were 46.36 cm in plots weeds managed three times per season (weeding at 15, 30, and 45 DAE). Only twice weeding (at 15 and 45 DAE) resulted in considerably taller average plant heights than control plots (no weeding). At 68 DAS, weed management strategies had no significant effect on average rice plant heights (p-value = 0.64) and at 82 DAS (p-value = 0.832), the observed variations in mean plant heights were not significant enough to support the influence of weed management strategies. SARO-5 cultivar had considerably shorter mean plant heights at 40, 54, 68 and 82 DAS (p < 0.001) than the other cultivars, despite the fact that the rest of the cultivars had statistically equal plant heights (Table 1.3). Generally the trend of plant height was increasing with increasing number of days.

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Table 1.2: Effects weeding regimes on vegetative variables of rice plants

Weeding regime	Mean Plant height(Cm)				Mean Number of Tillers/plant				Mean Number of Leaves/plant			
	40 DAS	54 DAS	68 DAS	82 DAS	40 DAS	54 DAS	68 DAS	82 DAS	40 DAS	54 DAS	68 DAS	82 DAS
Control	32.28	48.25	67.30	79.17	1.79	2.54	3.04	3.32	6.53	8.72	10.59	12.83
Weeding 15 DAE	32.60	49.32	68.29	80.15	2.00	2.93	4.18	4.31	7.15	10.58	13.84	16.67
Weeding 15 and 45 DAE	33.12	49.81	67.58	80.25	2.14	2.96	4.26	4.96	8.00	10.46	14.13	17.32
Weeding 15 , 30 and 45 DAE	33.68	46.36	67.20	78.43	2.02	2.92	4.41	5.08	7.61	9.95	14.20	17.91
Weeding 15 , 30, 45, and 60 DAE	34.30	46.98	66.32	79.09	2.08	2.93	4.64	5.37	7.31	10.25	14.81	18.30
Grand mean	33.196	48.144	67.338	79.418	1.986	2.856	4.106	4.608	7.32	9.992	13.51	16.60
LSD	2.678	2.674	2.562	3.668	0.208	0.371	0.565	0.611	0.918	1.635	1.643	2.256
Pvalue	0.172	0.058	0.640	0.832	0.023	0.14	<.001	<.001	0.053	0.053	<.001	<.001

DAE = Days after Emergence, DAS = Days after sowing, PV = P-value, and LSD = Least Significant Differences.

1.3.3 Number of tillers

There was statistical significant influence of weeding on rice number of tillers among rice cultivars at 40 days after sowing ($p = 0.023$) at the 5% significance level (Table 1.2). There was no significant influence of weeding on rice plant number of tiller at 54 days after sowing ($p\text{-value} = 0.114$). The weeded plots had no plants with more tillers than the non-weeded plots (controls). At 68 and 82 DAS, weeding had a significant impact on average rice number of tiller ($p < 0.001$). Plant number of tillers averaged 4.64 in plots where weeds were controlled four times (at 15, 30, 45 and 60 DAE), while number of tillers were 3.04 in unweeded (control) plots. Rice cultivars (Karimata, Kisegesi, Mbawambili, and SARO-5) were evaluated for their ability on producing plant tillers, at 68 days after sowing, there was statistical significant difference among rice cultivars ($p = 0.033$) (Table 1.3). Number of tillers was increasing with increasing number of days.

1.3.4 Number of leaves

Five weeding regimes were evaluated for their impact on rice leaf count and the results are presented in Table 1.2. Generally, at 5 % significance level, there was no significant influence of weeding on rice leaf count at 40 and 54 days after sowing ($p = 0.053$). But at 68 and 82 days after sowing, there was statistical significant influence of weeding on rice leaves count ($p\text{-value} < 0.001$) (Table 1.2). The results presented in Table 3.3, indicate that there was no significant differences between number of leaves of rice plants among different cultivars at 40, 54, 68 and 82 days after sowing. Number of leaves was increasing with increasing number of days.

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Table 1.3: Effects rice cultivars on vegetative variables of rice plants

Rice Cultivar	Mean Plant height (Cm)				Mean Number of Tillers /plant				Mean Number of Leaves/plant			
	40 DAS	54 DAS	68 DAS	82 DAS	40 DAS	54 DAS	68 DAS	82 DAS	40 DAS	54 DAS	68 DAS	82 DAS
SARO 5	21.84	31.53	40.04	52.10	2.285	3.419	5.46	5.92	8.25	11.35	11.25	21.25
MBAWAMB ILI	36.26	52.1	75.74	87.89	1.867	2.552	3.22	4.13	6.98	9.06	12.34	13.42
KARIMATA	37.22	54.6	79.46	91.92	1.881	2.632	3.61	3.95	6.72	9.95	13.93	14.77
KISEGESI	37.46	54.34	74.11	85.76	2.011	2.837	4.13	4.43	7.32	9.61	16.54	17.00
Grand mean	33.195	48.142	67.33 7	79.417	2.011	2.86	4.105	4.607	7.317	9.992	13.515	16.61
p-value	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	0.194	0.122	0.033	0.163	0.357	0.282	0.125	0.057
LSD	1.795	2.391	8.431	10.095	0.456	0.792	1.408	1.997	2.031	0.165	4.69	5.609

DAS = Days after sowing, PV = P-value, and LSD = Least Significant Differences.

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1.3.5 Duration to 90% grain maturity (days)

Five weeding regimes were evaluated for their influence on duration of rice to 90% grain maturity and the results are presented in Table 1.4. The influence of weed management practice was not significant at 5 % significance level ($p = 0.745$). Among the four rice cultivars, there was significant difference on duration to 90% grain maturity at $p < 0.001$. SARO-5 took longer duration to 90% grain maturity (125.3 days) while mbawambili, karimata and kisegesi took shorter duration (109.3 to 112.1 days) (Table 1.5).

Table 1.4: Effects of weeding regimes on yield components of rice crop.

Weeding regime	Days 90% maturity	Panicle Weight (g)	Grain Filling %	Weight of 1000 (g)
Control	114.2	4.142	89.60	31.29
Weeding 15 DAE	114.1	4.185	90.48	31.34
Weeding 15 and 45 DAE	114.2	4.442	91.36	31.57
Weeding 15 , 30 and 45 DAE	114.2	4.449	93.58	31.65
Weeding 15 , 30, 45, and 60 DAE	113.6	4.491	99.37	31.90
Grand mean	22.84	4.341	92.878	31.55
LSD	1.11	0.501	12.435	1.67
Pvalue	0.74	0.478	0.52	0.948

DAE = Days after Emergence, DAS = Days after sowing, PV = P-value, and LSD = Least Significant Differences.

1.3.6 Panicle weight (gm/panicle)

Results for the panicle weights of rice plants grown under varying weeding regimes are presented in Table 1.4. At 5 % significance level, there was no significant influence of weeding regimes on rice panicle weights (p -value = 0.478). Table 1.5 indicates panicle weights of different rice cultivars investigated under this study. Among rice cultivars studied, SARO-5 produced significantly lowest panicle weights (3.6g) whereas Karimata producing the highest (6.05g) panicle weights (p -value = 0.021).

Table 1.5: Effects of rice cultivars on yield components of rice crop.

Rice Cultivar	Days 90% maturity	Panicle Weight (g)	Grain Filling (%)	Weight of 1000(g)
Saro 5	125.3	3.16	88.73	28.91
Mbawambili	109.3	3.97	91.80	31.26
Kisegeese	112.1	4.16	95.48	31.67
Karimata	109.3	6.05	95.51	34.35
Grand mean	114	4.335	92.8	31.55
LSD	1.00	1.59	2.28	1.49
p-value	<0.001	0.021	<0.001	<0.001

DAS = Days after sowing, PV = P-value, and LSD = Least Significant Differences,

1.3.7 Grain filling

Grain filling (%) of rice was not significantly influenced by weeding regimes applied in this study (p -value = 0.52)(Table 1.4). Grain filling (%) of the studied rice cultivars varied significantly (p -value <0.001). The

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significantly higher grain filling observed was 95.51 for Karimata and the lowest was 88.73 for SARO 5 (Table 1.5).

1.3.8 Weight of 1000 seeds (gm)

The 1000 seed weight of rice was not significantly affected by weed management practices (Table 3.4) used under this study (p -value = 0.948). The studied rice cultivars (Karimata, Kisegesi, Mbawambili, and SARO-5) had statistically significant difference weights of their 1000 seeds (p -value <0.001) (Table 1.5).

1.3.9 Rice Grain yield (t/ha)

Five weeding regimes were evaluated for their influence on rice grain yield. Figure 1.4 shows the trend of rice grain yield across weeding regime. In ANOVA the results indicated there was statistical significant difference at 5 % significance level (p -value <0.001), where by weeding for at least two times (T3, T4 and T5) per season demonstrates positive effect on rice grain yield.

T1 = Control (no weeding), T2= Weeding at 15DAE, T3= Weeding at 15 and 45DAE, T4= Weeding at 15, 30 and 45DAE, T5= Weeding at 15, 30, 45 and 60DAE. DAE = Days after rice emergence.

Figure 1.2: Error bar chart for mean rice grain yield and weeding regime

Among the four rice cultivars, rice grain yield of KARIMATA (2.92 t/ha) was significantly higher, followed by Mbawambili while SARO-5 variety had the lowest net grain-weight (1.77 t/ha). The influence of rice cultivars towards yield was significant at 5 % significance level (P -value <0.001)(Fig. 1.3).

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Figure 1.3: Error bar chart for mean rice grain yield and rice cultivars.

1.3.10 Rice Straw dry weight (t/ha).

Five weeding regimes were evaluated for their effect on rice straw dry-weight and the results showed any of the weeding regime under this study caused significantly higher straw dry weight of rice plants (P-value<.001).Fig.1.4 shows the trend of rice straws drymatter over weeding regime.

T1 = Control (no weeding), T2= Weeding at 15DAE, T3= Weeding at 15 and 45DAE, T4= Weeding at 15, 30 and 45DAE, T5= Weeding at 15, 30, 45 and 60DAE. DAE = Days after rice emergence.

Figure 1.4: Error bar chart for mean rice straw dry matter and weeding regime

The results for rice straw dry weight of different cultivars are presented in Fig.1.5. There was no significant differences in straw weight of different cultivars (P-value = 0.672).

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Figure 1.5: Error bar chart for mean rice straw drymatter and rice cultivars.

1.3.11 Weed dry biomass and density

Weed total drymatter and individual weed species, Ps – *Paspalum scrobiculatum* and Ir- *Ischaemum rugosum* had the highest drymatter and there was statistical significant different difference (P - Value < 0.001) among the weeding regimes, in which control plots recorded the highest value and weed free plots with lowest value. But other weed species which are Fm- *Fimbristylis miliacea* (p = 0.015) and Cr – *Cyperus rondus* (P - Value = 0.011) showed significant differences (Table 1.6).

Table 1.6: Effect of weeding regimes on weed species

Weeding Regime	Dry Weights of Weed Species (t/ha)						Tw	Total weed count/m ²
	Ac	Cr	Fm	Gp	Ir	PS		
Control	0.09	0.04	0.13	0.41	0.96	1.22	2.85	194.7
Weeding 15 and 45 DAE	0.02	0.01	0.08	0.28	0.18	0.39	0.97	171.0
Weeding 15 DAE	0.02	0.00	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.11	0.27	194.3
Weeding 15 , 30, 45, and 60 DAE	0.01	0.00	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.13	171.8
Weeding 15 , 30 and 45 DAE	0.01	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.19	190.1
Grand mean	0.03	0.010	0.066	0.162	0.246	0.368	0.882	184.38
LSD	0.045	0.028	0.06	0.282	0.497	0.257	0.694	39.41
P-value	0.40	0.011	0.015	0.240	0.002	<.001	<.001	0.24

DAE = Days after Emergence, P-value = probability value, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, Ir = *Ischaemum rugosum*, Fm = *Fimbristylis miliacea*, Cr= *Cyperusrondus*, Tw = total weed dry weight, Ps = *Paspalum scrobiculatum*

The weed density was affected significantly among rice cultivars (P - Value <0.001) where Karimata cultivar recorded the lowest mean density of 151.5 weeds/m² while total and individual weed species dry mater had no significance differences (Table 1.7).

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Table 1.7: Influence of rice cultivar on weed species

Rice Cultivar	Dry Weights of Weed Species(t/ha)							Total weed count/m ²
	Ac	Cr	Fm	Gp	Ir	PS	Tw	
KARIMATA	0.043	0.02	0.05	0.34	0.13	0.41	0.99	151.5
SARO 5	0	0.00	0.07	0.15	0.40	0.17	0.79	188.5
MBAWAMBILI	0.034	0.00	0.06	0.08	0.31	0.43	0.91	198.4
KISEGESI	0.044	0.02	0.07	0.09	0.14	0.46	0.82	199.1
Grand mean	0.030	0.01	0.062	0.016	0.245	0.036	0.877	182.35
LSD	0.04	0.025	0.054	0.252	0.444	0.23	0.621	35.24
p-value	0.104	0.156	0.898	0.147	0.535	0.062	0.908	<.001

P-value = probability value, and LSD = Least Significant Differences, Ir = *Ischaemum rugosum*, Fm = *Fimbristylis miliacea*, Cr = *Cyperus rondus*, Tw = total weed dry weight, Ps = *Paspalum scrobiculatum*

1.3.12 Relative yield loss (%)

Relative yield loss had statistically significance differences among rice cultivars (P - Value = 0.02) in which Karimata cultivar recorded the lowest yield loss and the highest yield loss recorded in SARO5 (Fig. 1.6).

Figure 1.6: Rice relative yield loss in rice cultivars

1.3.13 Correlation analysis

Correlation of weed drymatter and grain yield had significant negative relationship (p<.001, R2 = 0.2691)(Fig. 3.7).If weed drymatter increases the rice grain yield drops.

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Figure 1.7: Relationship between rice grain yield and total weed dry weight

1.4 DISCUSSION

Among the weed species observed in the experimental field, *Paspalum scrobiculatum*, was the most dominant followed by *Ischaemum rugosum*. *Paspalum scrobiculatum* had the highest summed dominance ratio which was linked to its contribution in competition and reducing crop yield. Similar results were reported by Sunyob *et al.* (2012) detected that grasses were dominant in the rice fields. But Anwar *et al.* (2012) also recorded dominance of broadleaf weeds in their experimental rice field. The dissimilarity in weed community might be due to differences in weed seed bank structure between experimental sites (Varsha *et al.*, 2019).

A crop plant's capacity to outcompete weeds is gauged by its relative yield loss. According to this study, the Karimata rice cultivar, which was followed by the Mbawambili cultivar in terms of relative yield loss, had the greatest capacity to outcompete weeds. Similar to the findings of this study regarding rice varieties, it was also demonstrated that droopy-plant-type rice varieties with long leaves exhibit a high early growth rate, faster canopy covering, tall, high tillering ability, efficient growth resources utilization, and early maturing encounter less competition from weeds because they provide weeds with less space to grow (Awan *et al.*, 2018; Arefin *et al.*, 2018). These traits have been observed in Karimata rice cultivars for its competitive ability as evident in gaining higher panicle weight, grain filling percentage and 1000seeds weight. Differences in weed competitiveness between rice cultivars have previously been reported (Rahman *et al.*, 2017). The cultivar competitive ability not only depends on its characteristics, but also affected by the weed species and abundance. Among rice cultivars, Karimata showed the lowest relative yield loss, which indicates its higher weed tolerance potential. Apart from these characteristics, Karimata is also drought tolerant. Mahajan *et al.* (2014) proposed that competitive varieties need to be weed competitive and possess tolerance against other biotic and abiotic stresses.

The highest grain yield was observed in weed-free conditions compared to weedy conditions, regardless of cultivars due to no or less crop-weed competition for resources in weed-free plots as reported earlier in dry direct-sown, aerobic system of rice production (Shabi *et al.*, 2018). Differential weed suppressive abilities of rice cultivars were also reported by Chauhan *et al.* (2012) and Dass *et al.* (2017) concluded that rice-weed competition remained tougher for weeds having similar morphological characteristics with rice plants such as

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wild rice and weedy rice. The results showed that the average yield potential of local rice cultivars was higher than improved variety. This is because of low weed competitive ability and moisture stress conditions that affect dry matter assimilation by the crop. The longer growth duration of the rice variety also trigger higher grain yield loss. In this study local cultivars were found as strong weed suppressive/tolerant combined with high yield potential, except improved rice varieties, SARO 5. Environmental factors such as water availability greatly affect the performance of a particular crop plant/variety in a given environment. Naturally Crop weed competition is common and when crops are subjected to more competition, the physiological features of the growth and development of crops are typically altered. In a community, when the crop growth and development are altered due to competition, this result is brought by the differences in the use of essential environmental resources, especially the water, which disturb CO₂ in leaf mesophyll and leaf temperature (Islam *et al.*, 2021).

Dry biomass for both, crop and weeds determine the effect of competition in the plant community. Under this study weeding regimes had effects over dry matter accumulation, where in unweeded plots (control), weeds accumulated greater dry matter than rice crop. This study is supported by work of Mahajan *et al.* (2014) and Islam *et al.* (2021), reported that dry matter accumulation of weeds and rice crop were affected by weeding regimes; where in partial weeded plots weight of dry matter found higher for weeds and less for rice straws biomass. In weed free plots the rice crop accumulated greater dry matter, which is due to no or less competition for growth resources

1.5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Paspalum scrobiculatum and *Eschaemum rugosum* were the two most dominant weeds in this experiment, with grasses making up the majority of the dominant weeds and accounting for more than 60% of the total dominance ratio. This study found that there were differences in performance under weed pressure because of various varietal characteristics of rice. Compared to shorter rice cultivars like SARO 5, which have longer growth durations, Karimata, which have taller plants and somewhat shorter growth durations, performed better against weeds. Karimata had superior weed competitive ability as evidenced by lower/higher weed dry weight and low relative yield loss. Additionally, all cultivars studied showed better grain yields with two, three, and four weeding. For this reason, it is advised that farmers weed between 15 and 45 DAE in order to save operating costs, save time, and boost output. It is advised to conduct more thorough research to assess the competitive potential of karimata against weeds and the management strategies for the weed species *Paspalum scrobiculatum* and *Ischaemum rugosum*.

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